

Discourse on Reasoning and Corruption of Man: Lessons for Sustainable Leadership in Africa

Baraburu Goodnews Young

Department of Public Administration,
International Institute of Tourism and Hospitality,
Yenagoa. Bayelsa State
baraburug@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13826291>

Abstract

Discourse on reasoning and corruption of man: lessons for sustainable leadership in Africa is an investigation and interpretation of mental life of Africans, as it relates to learning experiences in leadership and guiding lessons for sustainable leadership in Africa. This paper is divided into seven (7) components for the purpose of clarity, brevity, precision, enthusiasm in reading and to be assessor's delight for the overall seeking of admiration in scholarship. The introduction provides an overview of the burden, the objective validity to attain and the notable lessons that predispose sustainable excellent leadership. A concise, precise and intriguing concept of reasoning is offered as a contextual guide to the discourse with a corresponding interpretations of the conceptual understanding of corruption for the enrichment of intellectual penetration and precision in comprehension. An outline of the devastating consequences of the lack of deep and appropriate reasoning in relation to the creation of corruptive tendencies in African leadership and the effects to African followership is a delightful narrative. In the centre and value of this discourse are the relevant and instructive lessons for sustainable excellent leadership in Africa. The conclusion summaries that the inherent glory in Africa that the world is patiently waiting for is a new quality of humanity of the African race that the mystery is in deep reasoning for leadership transformation which is the general good of Africa

Keywords: Reasoning; Corruption, Sustainability, Leadership

Introduction

Reasoning is one of the greatest, highest and priceless endowments that God boundlessly offers to man in order to nurture and nourish life and to interrogate himself and other men, problems, circumstances, environment, etc, with a great hope and expectations to find answers to the human questions. Reasoning is infinite in measurement but its infinity in existence does not carry a corresponding capacity in finding solutions to the problems of man. Reasoning is abundant but limited in the precious arena of providing sustainable excellent leadership in Africa because of the corruption of Africans, importantly, the African leaders.

The history of reasoning is not only a reasoning in diversities, but a deep and progressive levels of development, highlighting chronological purpose across time and space to add meaning and quality to the foundation of life in the African space, through the engineering of an unparalleled rate of growth in human knowledge and understanding that actuates leadership transformation in

Africa. Every man reasons, for human beings are reasoning beings, including Africans. Every African relishes in thoughts, for reasoning is the greatest and most distinguished occupation of human mind and solution to the sustainable excellent leadership in Africa.

Understanding the Concept of Reasoning

Reasoning is the illumination of the mind by the human spirit depicting ideas, impressions, perceptions, emotions, etc. The New Webster's Dictionary (1997) defined reason as the ability to think logically, to understand, and to draw inferences. Reasoning is a sharp threshing mental light that stimulates and interrogates problems, needs, values, intrigues, opportunities, approaches, expectations, methodologies, and circumstances within the context of the present or the future, in order to give a positive direction to man.

Reasoning is a means to an end and not an end in itself. Reasoning is the vehicle to convey Africans and the continent of Africa to the paradise of leadership excellence and give her a glorious pride in the global community. Unfortunately, unguarded reasoning, lack of deep mental exertion and disdain for virtuous reasoning have miserably denied Africans and African leadership the mysteries and blessedness of transformative leadership in the continent. These evils of reasoning are the highways to corruption and systemic decay in the African continent.

Understanding the Concept of Corruption

Corruption begins from the privacy of personal thoughts and permeates the public space in both the immaterial and material worlds. Corruption as a concept is a mental product, a product of the mind. It is an idea, a mental construct or an abstraction depicting the phenomenon of evil. The New Webster's Dictionary (1997) defined corrupt inion as the state of being or becoming decayed, a state of deterioration, perversion or moral decay. Corruption is the perversion or devaluation of thoughts and the deployment of perverted or devalued thoughts whether to advantage or not. Corruption is the pollution of mental life or perversity of mental life. Corruption is the decay of mental life or decay of intellectual mind.

Evolution of corruption flows from perverted or devalued thoughts to words, communications, speeches, decisions, choices, conduct, actions, lifestyles, etc, in personal and public undertakings. The state or quality of perverted or devalued thoughts flourishing in the mental life is corruption but when perverted or devalued thoughts step out of the confine of mental life to flourish in the physical space is manifest corruption. Thus, corruption exists in both mental life (immaterial space) and physical life (material space), and the authority and power of corruption flows from mental corruption in the mental life to pervade the physical life. Corruption in the mental life is theory while corruption in the physical life is practice, and both are of mutual equivalent. Corruption in the mental life is the other half of corruption in the physical life. Indeed, there is no single evil on earth that is not a product of corruption of thoughts or ideas. From the simplest to the greatest crime that mankind has ever committed in all generations across time and space is traceable to the corruption of thoughts or ideas, which is unguarded reasoning or disdain for virtuous reasoning. The evil or wickedness of African leaders to the African populace is only a dramatization of the corruption of thoughts or ideas, or corruption of reasoning of the African leaders that has made sustainable excellent leadership in Africa a mirage.

This discourse is to unveil the essential provisions in reasoning that is immune from corruption, and requisitely capable to promote and sustain transformative leadership in Africa. It is amazingly revealing and intriguingly necessary for African leaders to know that corruption of mental life is the ultimate destroyer and killer of everything that Africa holds in high esteem. Consequently, the mystery of sustainable leadership in Africa that blossoms in the greatest happiness for the greatest population of Africans is in the cultivation and nourishment of quality mental life or virtuous mental life among Africans.

Effects of Lack of Reasoning and the Nexus to Corruption

Good and quality thoughts or ideas are the secrets of sustainable excellent leadership as

Allen (2010) maintained that:

secret thoughts today, be it good or evil, will later become actual deed. He who unwearingly guard the portals of his mind against the intrusion of evil thoughts, and occupies himself with loving thoughts, will, when the season of their ripening comes, brings forth the fruits of gentle and good deeds (p.451).

Lack of deep reasoning corrupts mental life causing instability in leadership behavior and self-aggrandizement mentality which leads to abuse of governance in Africa. Failure to engage pure reflections corrupts moral rectitude and engenders unbridled and reckless acquisitive tendencies and ruination in leadership in both private and public life making the continent of Africa a mockery. Dearth of deep reasoning engenders ignorance of relevant and appropriate methodologies, techniques, approaches and tools to use in solving problems in the leadership experiences in Africa. Absence of pure reasoning corrupts attitudes and conduct that are prone to wickedness and perverted lifestyles that encourage sit-tight syndrome, coup d'états, and devilish tendencies among the African populace and the leaders. Sustainable excellent leadership in Africa will bring prosperity, happiness and fulfillment among the populace. "There is no striking a cheap bargain with prosperity. It must be purchased, not only with intelligent labour but with moral force" (Allen, 2010.). Virtuous reasoning is a catalyst to sustainability of people-oriented leadership in the continent of Africa and this discourse reveals the essential and appropriate lessons for leadership in the continent.

Lessons for Sustainable Leadership in Africa

One of the great lessons for African leaders to know is that the corruption of their mental lives or thought patterns is causing debilitating and painfully agonizing living experiences among the African populace, and has reduced a large population of Africans to miserable wretchedness in their living conditions. The mystery of statecraft that promotes leadership excellence is antithetical to corruption of thoughts or mental perversion, so African leaders must deliberately labour to free themselves from mental poverty or poverty of pure thoughts in order to enjoy the abundant secrets of statecraft that engenders transformation in leadership.

Plato (2003) in his famous book "The Republic", vehemently depicts that there is objectively good life, both for the individual and the state as nurtured by the idea that virtue is knowledge. When the supreme power in man coincides with the greatest wisdom and temperance, then the best laws

and the best constitution comes into being, but in no other way. He declared: “and there will be no end to the troubles of the states, or indeed of humanity itself, until philosophers become kings in this world, or till those we now call kings and rulers really and truly become philosophers, and political power and philosophy thus come into the same hands” (Plato, 2003, p. 192).

A change of thoughts will bring a change in leadership. When debased and devalued thoughts are abrogated to give room to fresh, pure and virtuous thoughts, African leaders will escape from the sit-tight syndrome, the pleasure of coup d’ etats, privatization of the public treasuries, unbridled acquisition of wealth and properties of state by family members of those in power, arrogance and abuse of power, extravagant ostentatious lifestyles of leaders and their cronies, corruption of the institutions of government, among others, and set a transformative mindset of leadership in the continent. On the 29th of May, 2023, at the inauguration ceremony of President Bola Ahmed Tinubu at Eagle square in Abuja, Nigeria, president Bola Ahmed Tinubu in his inaugural speech abrogated fuel subsidy without understanding the intricacies and implications of the abrogation, and the burning fury of the agents of destruction who are beneficiaries of the fuel subsidy, who are battle ready to destroy the economy. The fuel subsidy removal could have come later when the ailing refineries and the new refineries are put in functionality. This has put Nigerian economy in a theatre of war and Nigerians have been exposed miserably to unspeakable hardship, pain, horror, torment and misery. African leaders must understand the inherent value and implications of every national decision, policy and program in order to achieve and sustain excellent leadership in Africa. Because thoughts are figuratively contagious, the perversion of leadership thoughts of African leaders is directly responsible for the leadership misfortune and abuse of democratic opportunities which have resulted in starvation, poverty, sicknesses, diseases, miseries, illiteracy, unemployment, avoidable accidents, death and general underdevelopment in Africa. Nigeria, Liberia, Chad, Mozambique, Niger, Madagascar, Somalia, Sierra Leone, among others are typical signposts of African countries whose leadership must rise to confront the perversity of their thinking patterns to actuate purity in their world of thoughts or abstractions.

The growing decay of moral reflections and lifestyles on the part of African leaders, and the corresponding moral decadence in the African populace is attributable to the corruption of man. Morality is declining with rapidity because the integrity of thoughts and behavior is growing corruptively pervasive in both the African leaders and the led. To that effect, African leaders must encourage the cultivation of virtue and virtuous reasoning in leadership and followership in order to engineer a new breath of fresh life for Africa. Purity of character comes from purity of thoughts and it is the luxury of good leaders. “leaders who make a lasting difference are men and women of character who display a firm commitment to the public good, possess extraordinary political skills, and exhibit practical wisdom” (Magstadt, 2009,). Indeed the increasing incidences of disagreements, conflicts, quarrelling, fighting, crimes and cybercrimes, civil unrest, perverted behavior and wars in both governmental jurisdictions and the entire fabric of society in the African space is a product of the corruption of reasoning and unguarded patterns of reasoning. Corrupted thoughts and unguarded patterns of thinking are dangerous seeds and imminent social malady that predispose African community to ruination, therefore, African leadership must arise to cure this contagious mental disease. Azenabor (2010) averred that, “brain processes cause mental states but

do not exert any causal influence. They are mere by-products (i.e epiphenomenon) of bodily events. Epiphenomenalism is really an aspect of materialism. He maintained that, "the most momentous objection to epiphenomenalism consists in the enormous quality of prima facie evidence that the mental processes of human beings do make a difference to their lives" (Azenabor, 2010, p. 159).

It is plausible to situate the debasement of the thoughts of African leaders or the corruption of their reasoning patterns as the factor responsible for their failure to place Africa on the technological transformation platform, and overall development bliss. Devaluation of reasoning patterns of African leaders has denied them the advantage of leadership excellence requisite for technological wonder within the continent, and this had reduced Africans to a laughingstock in the global community. The onus is on African leaders to redeem Africa in mental reorientation, intelligent labour and moral force.

Allen (2010) asserted that:

a man had no power to be happy while thinking and acting selfishly, he cannot be unhappy while thinking and acting unselfishly. Wheresoever the cause is, there the effect will appear. Man cannot abrogate effects but he can alter causes. He can purify his nature, he can remould his character. There is great power in self-conquest; there is great joy in transforming oneself (p.505).

On 26th July 2023, a military coup d'état occurred in Niger, when General Abdourahame Tchiani, who served as the commander of the Nigerien presidential guard and his fellow coupists overthrown the democratically elected president Mohamed Bazoum and detained him and family members. Gen. Abdourahame Tchiani and the armed forces forcefully took over the leadership of Niger because of the lure and attractive lust for power due to the corruption of reasoning of the Niger military establishment. The Economic Community of West Africa States (ECOWAS) issued an ultimatum to the coup leaders threatening military intervention if deposed president Bazoum was not returned to power, but the coupists were adamant.

The Economic Community of West Africa States (ECOWAS) imposed sanctions that cut off Niger from many of its traditional trading partners, worsening chronic food insecurity among the vulnerable groups, and making living conditions excruciatingly miserable for the Nigerien. The military coup in Niger was another major blow to pro-democracy movement and sustainable leadership development in the Sahel. African leaders must engage and educate the military establishment to understand their constitutional role and the pressing need for them to protect and promote democratic opportunities and sustainable excellent leadership in the continent.

In the calculation of Aristotle (as cited in Magee, 1990), the general goal of human life is the good of man. He maintained that the general end or goal of good or primary human purposes is achieving a more adequate understanding of this basic goal (or set of goals) and working out the best way of pursuing and realizing it. Admonishment to African leaders is that mental corruption obstructs deep intellectual possibilities and hinders profound logical and technical understanding of methods and techniques in addressing challenging human problems; and this is the bane of African leaders in not having adequate comprehension that leadership intricacies begin with massive production

of goods and services, and processing of raw materials into finished goods for general human satisfaction and fulfillment. African leadership needs to know and demonstrate the value of food, clothing and shelter to life and human satisfaction, and correspondingly deplore statecraft to huge agricultural and related essential productions in order to address the basic needs and happiness of African community and add quality to sustainable leadership in Africa.

Around the world, people are becoming more assertive in demanding respect for their identities, their sense of worth and solution to their needs and challenges. Often, their demands are for social justice, for greater political voice and economic emancipation. This rising sharp consciousness is permeating the African space, and African leaders need to recognize the growing revolutionary pressures in Africa and abandon their primordial and traditional attachments to their narrow tribal proclivities and personal appetites for self-aggrandizement, because of the obvious growing risk of the luxury of that mentality. It is in the interest of African leadership to reengineer new and fresh mental attitudes and reasoning that will build strong national cohesion, patriotism, citizenship and identity, mantra of hope and pride that integrate and redound to national spirit in the consciousness of the nations of the continent of Africa. The African spirit of love, unity, oneness, brotherhood and the virtue of statehood should be the hallmark of the African community.

Locke (as cited in Magee, 2010) maintained that sovereignty ultimately remains with the people. Therefore, if a government begins to abuse the individual rights (i.e becomes tyrannical or ceases to defend them effectively or becomes ineffectual) the governed retain a moral right, after seeking redress through normal procedures and failing to obtain it, to overthrow the government and replace it with one that does the job properly. In 2006 when the constitutional provision for a transition of power in 2007, after president Olusegun Obasanjo completed his mandatory two (2) tenures, the luring temptation to relish on tenure elongation via a sinister constitutional tinkering to accommodation a third term, and perhaps a life presidency, enveloped the sensibilities of president Obasanjo and all entreaties to the contrary were jettisoned, at the risk of imminent national crises, and the president vigorously prosecute his sit-tight agenda to the chagrin of Nigerians.

The power of the presidency, the national resources and the presidential affiliations with cronies, sycophants and hangers-on had been exhaustively mobilized to wet the greedy appetite and sinister pleasures of a sit-tight public officer whose whims and caprices was the destruction of public trust. As the unmistakable gaze of impending national calamity confronted Nigerians on their faces, as it were, to draw political flavour from Rousseau's and Locke's prescriptions that power resides with the people, the public barometric pressure rose exceptionally to the abandonment of sectional, ethnic, class and idiosyncratic cleavages, and resulted in an affirmative unity of purpose against a national disaster. A national publication of a weekly news magazine, *The News*, May 01, 2006, opined that "ex-Nigerian heads of state, notably retired General Yakubu Gowon, Ibrahim Babangida, Muhamadu Buhari and Chief Ernest Shonekon met in Minna (Niger state) to deliberate on the state of the nation, especially third term agenda of president Obasanjo. It was resolved that the ex-leaders should work together to frustrate the third term bid because of the danger its actualization portends for Nigeria. The leaders affirmed that a third term bid for president Obasanjo is undesirable and so should never happen"

African leaders should avoid alienation from the people and alienation to the people in order to abrogate mutual distrust, hatred, disrespect, suspicion, fear, and lack of mutual confidence, which are products of corruption of thoughts or ideas for the purpose of enthroning sustainable excellent leadership that breeds peace and joy among the African citizenry. President Teodoro Obiang Nguema Mbasogo is a politician and former military officer who had served as the second president of Equatorial Guinea since 3rd August 1979 after seizing power from his uncle in a coup. He had ruled for 44 years and is 82 years old. Forbes Magazine had said that Teodoro Mbasogo had a net worth of US\$ 600 million, and is one of the world's wealthiest heads of state. He is one of the longest-serving heads of state (excluding monarchs) in the world. About 75% of the population live below the poverty threshold because president Mbasogo had pauperized the populace and made them most unfortunate. This is a critical signpost that African leadership needs a reengineering in reasoning and reasoning patterns that will actuate purification of leadership thoughts or ideas for both African leaders and followership. Corruption of thoughts is the corruption of life, and the corruption of leadership.

Conclusion

African leadership must thrive for a new quality of humanity of the African race that will blossom in good life, good Africans and good and modern living conditions, that will dramatize the treasure of happiness and the African pride via the veritable mechanism of sustainable excellent leadership. African leaders must avail themselves of the luxury of deep reasoning that is the mystery of transformation and progress for mankind. African leaders must shun corruption and fight the evil of corruption in mental life and practice because intellectual corruption produces material corruption and is the greatest mental disease that destroys Africans and hinders transformation. The quality of tomorrow's leaders lie in the character of today's followers. African leaders must rise to redeem the glorious destiny of Africa because the world and posterity is waiting for Africa which is the general good for Africa and the global community.

Recommendations

1. African leaders should engage in critical and strategic reasoning to experience deep understanding of new and quality leadership possibilities and experiences.
2. African leadership must focus on the technicality of old and new leadership problems and design contemporary methodologies and techniques capable of addressing the leadership needs but leadership is best learnt in the face of obstacles.
3. African leaders must make virtuous reasoning a commonplace and an essential component of living experiences because of the moral force in transformation.
4. Sustainable excellent leadership in Africa must meet the people's needs, expectations, hope and fulfillment.
5. New and fresh democratic opportunities and transformative leadership reasoning and reasoning patterns should be part of the informal and formal training institutions from cradle to grave to develop a new quality of African humanity.

6. In the African space, corruption in all ramifications must be declared an enemy of life by both the government and the people and therefore, hated, condemned, fought, killed and buried into extinction because unguarded reasoning is dangerous.
7. African leadership must not be attractive and ostentatious to discourage corrupt people, hence, new contractual bonds in leadership should be designed to removed remunerations for public officers so that voluntary patriots only will show interest in leadership.

References

- Allen, J. (2010). *Mind is the master*. New York: Penguin Group Inc.
- Azenabor, G. (2010). *Philosophical psychology*. Nigeria: Concept Publications.
- Ekekwe, E. N. (2008). *What has the world come to: The clash of civilizations or the end of History?* School of graduate studies public lecture. Port Harcourt: University of Port Harcourt Press.
- Hume, D. (2003). *A treatise of Human nature*. New York: Dover Publications, Inc.
- Mackie, J. L. (1990). *Ethics inventing right and wrong*. London: Penguin Books
- Magee, B. (2010). *The history of Philosophy*. London: Dorling Kindersley Limited.
- Mukherjee, S., & Ramaswamy, S. (2007). *A history of political thoughts: Plato to Marx*. New Delhi: Prentice-Hall of India Private Limited.
- Munroe, M. (1993). *Becoming a leader every one can do it*. USA: Pneuma Life publishing.
- Plato, (2003). *The republic*. (Lee, D. Trans.) London: Penguins Books Ltd.
- Plato, (2003). *Plato's theory of knowledge; The Theaetetus and the Sophist* (Cornford, F.M. Trans.) New York: Dover Publications. Inc.
- The New Webster's Dictionary of English Language (1997). USA: Lexicon Publications Inc.
- The News Magazine, (2006). May 1st Edition.